

GIGABIT ETHERNET FOR VOLUNTEER COMPUTING

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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The objective of this project is to collaborate with a team in Kansas City which has received funding from Mozilla Foundation to test new ways to exploit Gigabit-ethernet-to-the-home for distributed volunteer computing, using LHC@home as a test case. Such Gigabit Ethernet is being rolled out on an experimental basis by Google in certain neighbourhoods of a few US cities. Specific LHC@home jobs that require large I/O could provide a compelling science and education application for such high bandwidth connections. Building on a previous summer student project, this project will gather data on the performance of the infrastructure, and use this to model what sort of science applications could benefit, both for LHC@home and more broadly for volunteer computing projects in areas like climate change modelling or epidemiology.

ABSTRACT

Volunteer computing is a type of distributed computing in which computer owners can donate their spare computing resources (processing power, storage and Internet connection) to one or more research projects. Many existing volunteer computing platforms consist of millions of users, providing huge amount of memory and processing. Since the rapid growth in the volunteer computing projects, more researchers have been attracted to study and improve the existing volunteer computing system. Nowadays, the main challenge, that volunteer computing meets is raising more volunteers. It can be done by simplifying the process of installation required software. This paper describes approach taken to achieve that. It concerns the previous basis project, which was tried to be improved and its limitations. Then, it describes the application prototype that was built. Last part of this paper identifies the future possible work that can improve the application.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Volunteer computing is an arrangement in which people (volunteers) provide computing resources to projects, which use the resources to do distributed computing and/or storage. Typically volunteers are „ordinary“ citizens, who own Internet-connected personal computers. Projects are typically academic (university-based) and do scientific research.

The first volunteer computing project was GIMPS (Great Internet Mersenne Prime Search), which started in 1995. The Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing (BOINC) is the most widely used middleware system for volunteer computing.

The importance of volunteer computing should not be questioned:

- Because of the huge number (> 1 billion) of PCs in the world, volunteer computing can supply more computing power to science than does any other type of computing. That enable to perform many scientific research that could not be done otherwise.
- Volunteer computing power can't be bought; it must be earned. Thanks to that, even project with limited funding and no access to supercomputers, can get computing power, providing that they are interesting for the public.
- Volunteer computing encourages public interest in science, and provides the public with voice in determining the directions of scientific research.[1]

Main terms connected to the project are: BOINC, virtual machine, VirtualBox, CernVM WebAPI. Here is the short description of all of them:

- **BOINC** (Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing) – is an open-source software platform for computing using volunteered resources. It includes client, server, and web components, and APIs for connecting other components.[2]
- **VirtualBox** - is a free and open-source hypervisor for x86 computers currently being developed by Oracle Corporation. [3]
- **Virtual Machine** (VM) - is an emulation of a computer system. Virtual machines are based on computer architectures and provide functionality of a physical computer. Their implementations may involve specialized hardware, software, or a combination. [4]
- **CernVM WebAPI** - is an application that can interface for any browsers in order to provide real-time interaction with a CernVM Virtual Machine running in the host OS. This plugin identifies the hypervisors installed in the system and picks the most appropriate one to host the CernVM Guest OS. It then provides a simple interface to start/stop the VM and access it's configuration. [5]

2. BACKGROUND

During first 2 weeks of openlab programme I was familiarizing myself with the current state of project. There was a website “Challenge website” which was built 2 years ago by another student. At first I had to read the code of the application to find out how it functions. It turned out to be difficult and time-consuming, because project consists of many parts: Application Website, Application Webserver, CernVM WebAPI Daemon, CernVM Webmaster.

Figure 1. CernVM WebAPI components.

The following diagram displays the various components taking place in a typical CernVM WebAPI usage scenario:

- The **Application Website** is the website that wants to use the CernVM WebAPI. The application logic is written in JavaScript.
- The **Application Webserver** (in addition to serving the website) provides the Virtual Machine Configuration Point (VMCP), which is used to provide the configuration information for the virtual machine.
- The **CernVM WebAPI Daemon** is the binary application installed in the user's computer and is the one the javascript library interfaces with.
- The **CernVM Webserver** is the webserver inside CERN from which required information and data regarding CernVM WebAPI are stored.
- The **Hypervisor Website** is the website from which an appropriate hypervisor is downloaded from.
- The **Hypervisor** is an application installed in the user's computer and is the one where Virtual Machines will run.

After reading carefully the whole code, I tried to launch the website locally on my computer. During that process it turned out, that it is impossible, because of the fact that some parts of the CernVM WebAPI are broken. The cause is that some links to the CernVM Webserver are no longer available.

Moreover we came to the conclusion that some parts of the application could be designed and made in a better way. Therefore we decided to change the approach and perform the project in different way.

Figure 2. Challenge Website

3. PLAN AND EXECUTION

New approach to recreation an updated version of the Challenge Website was quite different. We decided to use the BOINC client in place of the WebAPI. That would allow us to use many functionalities of BOINC, instead of creating them on our own.

The objective is realized by using the XML RPC that BOINC clients already supports. To enable the browser to communicate with the BOINC client's TCP socket during development we decided to use a websockify proxy.

The resulting products are:

- A javascript library that implements the XML RPC.
- A document describing the XML RPC that are used.
- A html front end page.
- A javascript library supporting custom features used by the page.

The website, I was working on include the start/join button, the gear/settings button, status/progress indicators, VM connectors and login. The product I will provide will be reusable so that other sites can be easily created.

Below I place breakdown of subtasks I was working on:

1. Ping: A simple function that contacts the client and returns the version.
2. Client Install Logic: Poll the ping function and request to install the BOINC client on failure (similar to WebAPI).
3. Log: A function to read the "Event Log".
4. Display: Show the events on the page in both scrolling and history format.
5. Add project: Automate the add project function, requesting login or register (use project Website).
6. VBox Install Logic: Detect the error event that says VBox is not installed and request to install VBox.
7. Show the status of the tasks.
8. Verify the workflow that clicking on the "join" button results in a running Theory task.
9. The gear icon should show and change the BOINC computing preferences.
10. Make the page beautiful and add more status/progress features.

4. RESULTS

My first task was to check if it is possible to contact the client running on my machine. I have done it with the use of simple python script which returns the client version. Unfortunately it was not so straightforward as it may seem. Some commands, that can be executed by BOINC client, can be executed only when the user is authorized. I had many problems to achieve authorized status on my machine. It was caused by some problems with BOINC client configuration. The only solution was to use BOINC client compiled directly from source instead of using its downloaded version.

Then after installation of webservify I was working on BOINC client installation logic. I prepared javascript function which detects operation system on the user's computer and according to that, display the button to download BOINC client, which is proper for user's system. Next step after successful installation of boinc client is to detect if the user has Virtual Box installed. I have also prepared javascript function which provide the user with a button. When user clicks the button, then the proper version of Virtual Box (suitable for user's operation system) is downloaded and installed.

My task was also to write functions which send messages to client and then parse client's responses. This task was really time-consuming because it requires to parse all xml tags which occur in the response or find which tags can be important for us.

During my whole stay at CERN I managed to built a prototype of a new application. This prototype guides the user through the process of installation BOINC client and Virtual Box, which are proper for user's operation systems. The webapplication includes also some features from BOINC manager. It is possible to see running tasks, suspend/resume them etc., display charts, log to the project and update project.

5. CONCLUSION

After 8 weeks of work on the project I claim that its current state is a good base for future work. I managed to prepare basic functionalities, which can be later developed and improved. The application detects if user have already installed BOINC client and Virtual Box and if not then it installed them. The user can check status of tasks currently running on the machine and perform some actions on computation process, e.g. suspend, resume, see details etc.

There is still much what can be done with this project. Very important part will be to improve visual side of the application. It would be good if a Websocket will be added to the BOINC client (unfortunately it is out

of scope for this short term project). Moreover it is a possibility to move even all functionalities of BOINC Manager to the website applications.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

[1] - <https://boinc.berkeley.edu/trac/wiki/VolunteerComputing>

[2] - <https://boinc.berkeley.edu>

[3] – <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/VirtualBox>

[4] - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Virtual_machine

[5] - <https://github.com/wavesoft/cernvm-webapi/wiki>

